

Complexes of Schiff base 2-aminothiophenolsalicylidine and some neutral ligand with manganese-, cobalt- and zinc(II)

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The complexes of Schiff base 2-aminothiophenolsalicylidine having the stoichiometry MLX_3 , where $M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}$, and MLX , where $M = Zn^{II}$, $L =$ ligand, $X =$ neutral ligand (pyridine, quinoline, isoquinoline and γ -picoline) have been prepared. The ir spectra reveal tridentate nature of the Schiff base ligand and coordinated through N-atom of neutral ligand. The electronic spectra suggest the octahedral geometry except Zn^{II} which is tetrahedral. All the complexes except the complexes of Zn^{II} are paramagnetic.

In continuation to our earlier work, we prepare and characterise some complexes using the ligand 2-aminothiophenolsalicylidine with Mn^{II} , Co^{II} and Zn^{II} .

Elemental analysis of the complexes (Table 1) correspond to the formula MLX_3 ($M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}$) and MLX ($M = Zn^{II}$) where, $L =$ 2-aminothiophenolsalicylidine (ATPS) and $X =$ neutral ligand pyridine, quinoline, isoquinoline and γ -picoline. Molar conductance values of the complexes (less than $50 \Omega \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) suggest their non-electrolytic nature. The monomeric structure of the complexes is suggested by molecular weight measurement (Rast's camphor method).

Ir spectra of the Schiff base ligand (ATPS) show a broad and medium band at $3100\text{--}3000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, assigned to CH stretching vibration of aromatic ring. The band around 2700 cm^{-1} is attributed to intramolecular hydrogen bonded OH¹. The absence of this band in the complexes indicates the deprotonation of the ligand. The ligand at $\sim 2350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (SH)² shifted by $20\text{--}30 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the metal complexes, indicating the coordination through S atom. The ligand band of the Schiff base appearing at 1600 cm^{-1} (C=N) shifted to $\sim 1620\text{--}1630 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes, indicating the coordination through azomethine nitrogen³.

The characteristic phenolic band of the ligand at ~ 1789 (O-H) and 1230 cm^{-1} (C-O) shifted at ~ 1405 and 1330 cm^{-1} respectively in the complexes. This suggest the participation of phenolic group on complexation. The coordination of the Schiff base through O, N and S atoms to the metal ion is further indicated by the appearance of ν_{M-O} , ν_{M-N} and ν_{M-S} bands at $580\text{--}550$, $485\text{--}460$ and $370\text{--}345 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively, in the far-ir region⁴.

In the ir spectra of the complexes, the band at 1580 cm^{-1} due to neutral ligand (pyridine, quinoline, isoquinoline and γ -picoline) suggests the coordination through N-atom⁵. Further, the coordination of neutral ligand through N-atom is ascertained by the appearance of band at $\sim 1530 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu_{C=C} + \nu_{C-N}$.

The magnetic moment values of the Mn^{II} complexes (5.81–5.89 B.M.) indicate high-spin octahedral environment. The complexes show three weak absorption bands at ~ 14340 , 16560 and 20000 cm^{-1} assigned to the transitions ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(4G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(4G)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g, {}^4A_{1g}(4G)$ respectively, which supports the octahedral environment around Mn^{II} ion⁶. The magnetic moment values of the Co^{II} complexes (4.62–4.82 B.M.) are consistent with that of high-spin octahedral geometry around Co^{II} . The complexes show three bands at 9000 , 18700 and 23000 cm^{-1} , which can be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ transitions respectively.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the complexes*

Compd.**	M.p. °C	Colour	Metal % :		μ_{eff} B.M.
			Found/ (Calcd.)	—	
[Mn(ATPS)Py ₃]	>220	Yellow	10.68 (10.58)	5.81	
[Mn(ATPS)Qn ₃]	>238	White	8.51 (8.20)	5.86	
[Mn(ATPS)Iqn ₃]	>241	Yellow	8.61 (8.20)	5.83	
[Mn(ATPS)(γ -Pic) ₃]	>228	Violet	9.85 (9.79)	5.89	
[Co(ATPS)Py ₃]	>251	Black	11.34 (11.26)	4.62	
[Co(ATPS)Qn ₃]	>253	Violet	8.89 (8.75)	4.64	
[Co(ATPS)Iqn ₃]	>256	Black	8.85 (8.75)	4.78	
[Co(ATPS)(γ -Pic) ₃]	>253	Blue	10.62 (10.42)	4.82	
[Zn(ATPS)Py]	>218	Yellow	17.74 (17.60)	Dia	
[Zn(ATPS)Qn]	>222	Yellow	15.81 (15.51)	Dia	
[Zn(ATPS)Iqn]	>225	Gray	15.72 (15.51)	Dia	

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses.

**Py = Pyridine, Qn = quinoline, Iqn = isoquinoline, γ -Pic = γ -picoline; ATPS = 2-aminothiophenolsalicylidine.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. 2-Aminothiophenolsalicylidine was prepared by condensation of 2-aminothiophenol and salicylaldehyde in ethanol and the resulting yellow solid was crystallised from ethanol and dried under reduced pressure.

Note

Metal complexes : An aqueous ethanolic solution of the metal chlorides (0.05 mol in 40 ml), Schiff base ligand (ATPS; 0.05 mol in 40 ml) and neutral ligand (pyridine, isoquinoline, quinoline and γ -picoline; 0.15 mol in 40 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath for 30 min. The resulting solid was washed with ethanol and dried in vacuum desiccator over anhydrous CaCl_2 .

The metals were analysed by standard procedure. C, H, N were analysed by using CE-440 analyzer. The molar conductance in 10^{-3} M DMF solution was measured on a Systronic-303 conductivity bridge. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Beckman IR-20-A spectrophotometer and

electronic spectra on an Unicom SP-500 spectrophotometer. The magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature by Gouy method using diamagnetic correction with Pascal's constant.

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